

THE IMPACT OF HOUSING ON RURAL DEVELOPMENT

By

**AWOTAYO GBENGA, EDUN ABDULKAREEM, J. and
LAWAL LUKMAN. O.**

*School of Basic and Remedial Studies,
Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin, Nigeria.*

Abstract

Good housing is crucial to family life, physical and mental health, child development, employability, social and financial inclusion and the creation of sustainable balanced communities. Shortage of adequate housing virtually abounds in every country, particularly in the developing nations. The shortage is in both quantitative and qualitative terms. Planners and Geographers alike tend to use rural infrastructural development as a strategy to redress this problem. This study examines rural housing and economic development programme as a capacity building process at both the state and local level to support innovative housing and economic development which will result in tackling the problems of poverty, inadequate housing and lack of economic opportunities in the rural area.

Purposive sampling method was used and a 368 copies questionnaire were administered based on the population in the study area which is 1% of the target population. Chi-Square analysis was used to test the level of significance between the level of development income and the types of residential building in the study area. The study reveals that ($X^2_{cal} = 83.5$, $df = 8$ $P < 0.05$, $X^2_{table} = 15.507$) since $X^2_{cal} > X^2_{table}$) there is a positive relationship between the level of development (income) and the types of residential building in Isin L.G.A. The study also reveals that planning for integrated rural development without facts on rural basic needs has limited chances for success, no matter how hard we try in both policy formulation and implementation. This also calls for sustainable development which ensures a better quality of life for everyone now and for generations to come.

Key words: *Housing, Development, Nigeria, Sustainable, Rural*

Introduction and Justification for the Study

The discourse on rural housing in Nigeria is often dominated by concerns for poverty alleviation which is a huge disparity between rural and urban earning. According to the 2006 Census, about 70% of the Nigerian overall population live in rural areas, including smaller towns and villages. The drive for knowledge searching concerning sustainable development has brought up this research in order to determine the impact of qualitative housing on rural development in Isin L.G.A as a representative of the length and breadth of Nigeria.

Housing has a key role in creating sustainable community and also is one of the fundamental needs of human being. The key factor is ensuring that housing which meets people's need is available and accessible since everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well being of himself and of his family. This basic standard of living include's housing. Housing is ranked second to food in terms of human needs and has a close link with the body. Housing, as a unit of the environment has a profound influence on the health, social behavior and general welfare of the community. It reflects the cultural, social and economic values of a society because it is the best physical and historical evidence of civilization in a country (Olotuah, 2000).

The term 'development' refers to the conscious action by utilizing, in a co-ordinated way, the resources available to a given political unit. Rural Development is required to protect the integrity of sites, buildings, districts, structures and local importance in venturing into any undertaking that might cause any beneficial or adverse changes to these properties. The provision of adequate housing in any country is very vital as housing is a stimulant of the national economy. Onibokun, (1985) notes that decent housing is one of the basic needs of every individual, the family and community in general. Adequate housing implies that inhabitants are provided with adequate space

and facilities and are protected from the elements and other threats to health such as structural hazards, disease vectors and the physical safety of the occupants must be guaranteed. As housing increases, population increases and the economic activities also increases and vice versa. Adequate housing is an expression of cultural identity and diversity. Therefore, housing can be seen as a major sector having strong social connection in the national economy. The economic sector cannot be independent of housing for a successful implementation and meaningful result.

There are numerous problems facing housing sector in developing countries. Among which include inadequate social amenities, inflation and high cost of building materials and high cost of transportation of goods. In Nigeria, like in many other developing nations of the world, housing problems are multi dimensional. The problems of population explosion, continuous influx of people from the rural to the urban centers, and the lack of basic infrastructure required for good standard of living have compounded housing problems over the years. Access to this basic need by the poor who constitute the largest percentage of the world population has remained a mirage and it needs to be critically addressed.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study examines the impact of housing on socio-economic development of rural communities. This aim was achieved with the following objective:

- (i) Identify the characteristics of the housing types within the area;
- (ii) Identify the relationships between housing and rural development.
- (iii) Proffer possible solution(s) to the identified gaps.

Study Area

The study area is Isin Local Government Area in Kwara State. It covers about 990sq.km with a population projection of 118,000 (NPC, 2006) with her headquarter at Owu-Isin.

The area is divided into eleven wards which include Isanlu-Isin I, Isanlu-Isin II, Ijara-Isin, Iwo, Olla, Edidi, Oke-Onigbin, Alla, Owu-Isin, Oke-Aba, and Pamo/Sabaja/Oba. The people of this area are a sub-group of Yoruba of Igbomina. They are located in Kwara-South of the state.

Methodology

The method adopted in collecting data in this study is majorly by primary means i.e. through administration of structured questionnaire. Purposive sampling method was adopted to determine the section of the population and group of people to be administered the questionnaires. A total of 368 questionnaires were administered based on the population in the study area which is 1% of the target population. Systematic sampling techniques were used in obtaining the desired information through questionnaires administration and oral interviews from the respondents and it allowed for easy and unbiased administration of the questionnaires in the study area.

1000-3000	55	71.4	29.4	40	13.2	152
4000-6000	88	30.7	12.5	15	13.2	Total
7000-9000	18	17.8	7.4	2	7.8	33
Above 10000	15	9.2	3.8	-	4.0	17
Total	199	82	87			368

**THE IMPACT OF HOUSING ON RURAL
DEVELOPMENT**

Table 1: Questionnaires Allocation

S/No	Ward in Isin L.G.A	Population	No of Questionnaires
1.	Isanlu-Isin I) Isanlu-Isin II)	6554	64
2.	Ijara-Isin	5260	52
3.	Iwo	4034	40
4.	Olla	3388	33
5.	Edidi	1955	19
6.	Pama/Sabaja/Oba	2438	24
7.	Oke-Onigbin	3989	39
8.	Alla	1463	14
9.	Oke-Aba	4180	41
10.	Owu-Isin	4203	42
Total		37,364	368

Table 1. Federal Republic of Nigeria Population Census (1991).

Result and Findings

$$\text{Formula } x^2_{\text{cal}} = \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where x^2 = **Chi-square**

O = Summation

O = Observed value

E = Expected value

Table 2: Chi-Square Results on Types of Residential Buildings

Income per Month	Types of Residential Buildings						Total
	Bungalow		Storey Building		Others		
	O	E	O	E	O	E	
<1000	70	70.3	30	29	30	30.7	130
1000-3000	63	71.4	29	29.4	40	31.2	132
4000-6000	33	30.3	8	12.5	15	13.2	56
7000-9000	18	17.8	13	7.4	2	7.8	33
Above 10000	15	9.2	2	3.8	-	4.0	17
Total	199		82		87		368

**THE IMPACT OF HOUSING ON RURAL
DEVELOPMENT**

At level of significance (alpha level) 8 0.05

$$X^2_{\text{tab}} = 15.507$$

Chi square calculated X^2_{cal}	Chi square tabulated X^2_{tab}
83.50	15.507

The variation between level of development (income) and residential building was found to be statistically significant. since ($X^2_{\text{cal}} (83.50) > X^2_{\text{tab}} (15.51)$) $P > 0.05$ this implies that there is a positive relationship between the level of development (income) and the types of residential building in Isin L.G.A. This not was by accident as it has been confirmed statistically using chi-square analysis.

Table 3: Chi-Square output on condition of Buildings

Type of Ownership	Condition of Buildings								Total
	Good		Fair		Poor		Dilapidated		
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Owned (Landlord)	51	35.9	29	42.1	3	2.9	5	7.1	88
Rented (Tenant)	57	65.6	82	77	5	5.3	17	13.1	161
Co-Owned	42	48.5	65	56.9	4	3.9	8	9.7	119
Total	150		176		12		30		368

**THE IMPACT OF HOUSING ON RURAL
DEVELOPMENT**

At level of significance (alpha level) 8 0.05

$$X^2_{tab} = 15.507$$

Chi square calculated X^2_{cal}	Chi square tabulated X^2_{tab}
16.1	12.59

The relationship exists between condition of the buildings and the types of house ownership in the study area was found to be statistically significant. Since $(X^2_{cal} (16.01) > X^2_{tab} (12.59) P > 0.05$

TABLE 4: Housing Facilities

Facilities Available	Number of Building	Percentage
Toilet / Bathroom	198	46.3
Pit Toilet	96	22.4
Kitchen	134	31.3
Total	428	100

The available facilities in the housing unit determined, the quality of the building which also depicted the standard of living of the occupants. Table 4 shows the variations in the facilities availability in the housing unit.

TABLE 5: Refuse Disposal System

Refuse Disposal System	Number of Building	Percentage
Dust Bins	162	44.0
Incinerator	10	2.7
Burning	152	41.3
Dumping into Streams	24	6.6
Others	20	5.4
Total	368	100

The survey on refuse disposal reveals that 44% of the sampled household used dust bins which is highest, 2.7% incinerators, 41.3% preferred to burn the refuse, 6.6% dump their refuse into streams while 5.4% prefers to use other means of disposal such as burying the refuse. This is an indication that over 50% of the population uses refuse disposal system that poses serious risk to the health and development of the area which needs urgent attention.

Table 6: Household Size

Household size	Number of Building	Percentage
1-3	85	23.1
4-6	178	48.4
7-9	71	19.3
10-12	24	6.5
13and above	10	2.7
Total	368	100

About 59% of sampled the respondents had household size of between 4-6 members, while only 9% had household size of above 10 members . Therefore, since the household size is quite low, it will increase the standard of living in term of the quality since the little income collected will be spent on a few people.

Moreover, the study also revealed that 259% had been living in the study area for more than 21 years, while about 50% of the respondents had been living in Isin LGA for between 10-15 years. Also, 12.2% between 16-20years, 21.2%'between 11-15 years while 27.7% between 6-10 years and only 14.4% had been living in the area for less than 5 years. This scenario implies that people are moving into the area continuously and if this continues at this rate, more development will set in.

The Education status of the respondents shows that 24% had primary education, 52% had acquired secondary education while only 5.4% of the

respondents had tertiary education and 18% had no education at all. The implication of this is that 82% of the sampled population can read and write.

The occupational structure of respondents reveals that 41% are farmers, 20.7% are civil servant, 21.5% are students, and 8.9% are unemployed while 2.7% are professional and remaining 5.2% engaged in other activities. This reveals that the study area is predominantly rural since they are mostly agriculturist.

The income distribution of the respondents reveals a very low income structure with highest monthly earner of above N10, 000.00 accounts for 4.6% of the respondents. The highest percentage of respondents of 36% earn between N1000-N3, 000.00. This shows that the monthly income of the people in the study area is low which is a reflection of the standard of living of the people.

The building type which respondents live in reveals that 54% live in bungalow, while 22% live in storey building and 23% other types of building such face-nue-and-face-you. The type of ownership shows that 25% of the sampled household owned their buildings, 45% are rented while 29% are co-owned.

The age of building shows that 29% of building are above 21 years of age, 13.6% between 16-20 years, 21.7% between 11-15years, 27.4% between 5-10 years and the remaining 8% below 5 years. This indicates that most of the houses in the study area are relatively old.

The building materials of the house show that 26% of the buildings are made of mud clateritel, and mud bit plaster while 73% is made of concrete (block). The housing facilities show that 46% of the building has toilet/bathroom, 22% has pit toilet, 31 % has kitchen.

The source of water supply in the various houses of the respondents reveals that 18% of buildings make use of pipe borne water, 630/0 use well,

implication is that the well serves as the major source of water to most of the houses. The Power Holding Company remains the main source of electricity in the study area.

Conclusion

The purpose of housing in rural development is to build capacity at the local level for rural dwellers. This also implies that rural development should have the rural man as the center piece as envisaged in the fourth National Development-Plan.

Therefore, it should be noted that planning for rural development should be a continuous exercise, since continuous survey and updating will reveal the gaps and deficiencies in rural welfare which will now prompt appropriate corrective measures in the rural development. This paper thus recommends that government should formulate purposeful rural development policy that can prevent rural majority from being left behind in the development process, and that minimises rural-urban drift and its attendant problems

Finally, there is no single solution to the complex issue of rural housing problems. However, housing finance is a key instrument in moving towards a solution, with the support of government political will.

REFERENCES

- National Population Commission* (1991), *National Population Census 1991 National Summary*. Federal Government Gazette, Abuja
- National Population Commission* (2006), *National Population Census 1991 National Summary*. Federal Government Gazette, Abuja
- Olutuah, A.O. (2000) "Housing Low-Income Civil Servants in an Emergent State Capital" the case study of Ado-Ekiti, Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria.

Onibokun, P (1985) *Housing in Nigeria*" Published by (NISER) Ibadan.